

New Normal for Pharmaceutical Business Management during the Pandemic

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Abstract

The pharmaceutical industry has reached a new zenith every time the world has faced medical calamities. Unfortunately, its efforts in combating the novel coronavirus are falling short, as the disease is capturing the world rapidly. The unfortunate outbreak of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has not only caused a major slump in the global economy, the way of doing business is also expected to undergo major changes. And, the pharmaceutical industry as well failed to escape this pandemic.

This paper dives deep into the nuances of how the basics and ‘new normals’ of business management will change for the pharmaceutical industry in the world that is harshly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. The research takes an exploratory approach to understand how this pandemic will change prominent business operations viz. production, supply chain management, and marketing, for pharmaceutical companies.

It also discusses the immediate steps that they can take to transform production, supply chain management, and how marketing operations can be digitized to thrive stronger to meet the changing market needs.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical Business during COVID-19, Pharmaceutical Business Management, Pharmaceutical Industry during Pandemic, Pharmaceutical Business Operations

1. Introduction

In December 2019, the outbreak of COVID-19 was first diagnosed in Wuhan, China, and today it has spread across 190 countries around the world. Though it has been over five months since the World Health Organization (WHO) declared a pandemic, some of the largest of the emerging economies are still on the upstroke of the COVID-19 outbreak. As the

daily count of COVID positive patients continues to increase, not only patients but the world economy has also seem to have succumbed to this pandemic.

As an economic downturn of the COVID-19 pandemic, businesses across the world are witnessing a major crisis, as most industry giants such as Uber, Zomato, and AirBnB, have taken harsh measures to keep their businesses afloat. Nearly all the industries have been hit bad due to this pandemic, and the pharmaceutical industry is no exception. Most pharmaceutical businesses are witnessing severe challenges in implementing their business continuity plans due to major disruptions in production and supply chain operations.

Since the outbreak of influenza and the pandemic of 1918, the COVID-19 pandemic has become the most serious global public health crisis of this generation. During their investigation of discovering potential therapies and treatments for COVID-19, multiple clinical trials are being launched worldwide. This highlights the capability as well as the need of today's healthcare industry to find significant evidence even in the middle of this COVID-19 pandemic. However, no therapies have been shown effective to date.

A significantly high number of pharmaceutical companies are taking centre stage in the Covid-19 fight, with their dedicated effort for finding a vaccine that can make the world COVID-free. On the other hand, most of the leading pharmaceutical firms are bracing themselves to contribute to lightening the COVID-19 burden on the world to make it a better space.

For instance, Bayer AG - a German multinational pharmaceutical and life sciences company - donated over three million tablets of Resochin, which is a generic antimalarial, to the United States. Eli Lilly and Company - an American pharmaceutical company - took a great initiative to help diabetic patients understand, through full-page adverts in various papers, how they can benefit from its support during such a financially difficult time.

While a significantly high number of pharmaceutical companies are investing in research & development to discover an effective drug or vaccine to fight COVID-19, running a business that is profitable has become a major roadblock for a huge number of businesses around the world. While globalization has liberated the boundaries for businesses to make profits, the time has come to deal with the same factor which has become a barrier for pharmaceutical businesses around the world.

2. Literature Review

Most pharmaceutical businesses had been concentrating all their operations on the discovery of deadly diseases like cancer, along with many other rare medical conditions. However, considering the gravity of this pandemic, the pharmaceutical industry is most likely to

introduce tectonic shifts in its business strategies and business development models in the coming years.

The unprecedented impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic have caused a major slump in the economic growth of the world. According to a report published by the Federation of American Scientists (FAS) on May 01, 2020, global trades are likely to fall from 13% to 32% and economic growth of the world may get hampered by nearly 2% per month, if the current situation continues to persist.

Western regions such as the United States of America and the entire European Union and the United Kingdom are known to have hit worst. However, Japan's economy has also sunk into recession as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) declined to an annualized 3.4 percent in the January-March quarter.

Another report published by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the prevalence of drug use was estimated to be quite low - around 5% and the number of drug users was nearly 210 million across the world. However, the number increased by more than 30% to reach 271 million, attributing to the ballooning population, resulting in a significant rise in demand for pharmaceutical products. The use of drugs rose substantially between 2009 and 2017, however the pandemic has changed the dynamics for the pharmaceutical industry.

In August 2019, a white paper was published by The United States Pharmacopeial Convention, and it found that the condition of medicines stock-outs and essential drug shortages is disturbingly commonplace, as above 2 billion in the world lack access to pharmaceuticals and medicines that can prevent diseases and deaths. The paper also projects that local production of pharmaceutical products is emerging as a vital factor that will fill a market gap for essential medicines with low profit margins.

Another research paper written by researchers at the Ritsumeikan University, Japan, focuses on "International Strategy for Sustainable Growth in Multinational Pharmaceutical Companies". The study advocates the three-stage theory of internationalization which depicts the S-curve relationship, along with the entrepreneurial theory in its theoretical implications. Practically, the study proposes that pharmaceutical companies should shift their focus on specific regional markets and adopt new business strategies to cater to customers' evolving needs in order to secure higher sales.

Most of these research and white papers highlight the importance of understanding the new definitions of 'globalisation' and benefits of expansion of local production facilities for pharmaceutical businesses to win in the foreseeable future.

3. Dependence of Overseas Production and Potential Drug Shortages

The current situations indicate a higher possibility of a majority of countries stockpiling pharmaceutical raw materials strictly for domestic use and putting restrictions on their exports. This will reflect in a mounting number of drug manufacturing companies witnessing significantly serious challenges in maintaining their inventories.

3.1 China and India: Largest Suppliers of Pharma Raw Materials

The worldwide outbreak of COVID 19 has revealed the world's acute dependence on China, and India in some cases, when it comes to carrying out production of most goods and products; pharmaceutical products are no exception to this. The entire world depends on China for active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), which are also referred to as bulk drugs that are commonly used in all pharmaceutical products and supplements.

The United States Cellular Corporation projected in one of its latest reports that China outranked The United States to become the world's largest supplier of APIs or bulk drugs. For example, the report estimated that nearly three-fourth of heparin - an anticoagulant - required per month in the United States was sourced from China. This overall, not restricting to the particular example, indicates the massive impact China's raw materials have on the global pharmaceutical industry.

In another example, emergency use authorization for chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine was issued recently by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has officially issued. These drugs have been long-time proven and are known to be the most commonly used medications for the treatment of malaria, and India supplied these drugs to over 40 countries since April 2020.

As China enjoys its virtual monopoly in the supply of APIs or bulk drugs, the outbreak of COVID-19 and deteriorating relationship with China can potentially result in grave consequences - mainly severe shortages in the supply of essential drugs. The entire pharmaceutical industry is realising the downside of their reliance of India, and majorly on China, for the production of their pharmaceutical products.

3.2 Global Travel Restrictions and Factory Closures Impact Production

The entire world has been locked down and strict regulations that prohibit factories from operating have had a significant impact on the production for pharmaceutical business. This does not only amplify the drawbacks of the world's dependence of foreign-sourced drugs but it also aggravates drug shortages during a global pandemic response.

Though the United States and Europe remain home to most API manufacturing plants today, India and China account for nearly one-third of the global operations, further magnifying the world's dependence of foreign-sourced drugs. However, most countries are initiating a new trend of 'buy local', which is likely to emerge as a silver lining for pharmaceutical manufacturing plants. Yet, there is still a high level of anxiety among businesses due to travel restrictions and factory closures.

Furthermore, most private enterprises in the global pharmaceutical industry seem to be reluctant from investing in research & development due to the uncertainty that the near future beholds. Nevertheless, most governments also seem to be inclined towards investing in the sector for reviving operations. Most public sector institutions are likely to boost their investments in technology to scale up pharmaceutical production while controlling pollution as well as prices to compete with Chinese companies and reduce their dependence on China's raw materials.

4. Supply Chain Disruptions for Pharmaceutical Businesses and their Global Footprints

Pharmaceutical industry, apart from its commercial aspects, has always devoted its services to the wellbeing of patients. One of the most important parameters of success for a pharmaceutical business is that the right drug or supplement is delivered to the right customer at the right time. This is nothing but the indication of efficient supply chain management. However, the global pandemic has posed a formidable risk not only to human life but also to the supply chain and logistics operations across the pharmaceutical industry.

COVID-19 has triggered pharmaceutical businesses from the Western countries to mitigate their over-reliance on the raw material supplies from China and manage their supply chains by shifting to other developing regions with manufacturing advantages such as Africa, Asia, and Latin America. India is among the very few countries that can match China's manufacturing scales and efficiencies, which will create new opportunities for all stakeholders in the global pharmaceuticals industry.

4.1 Global Operations and Evaluation of Supply Chain Management

Though it is absolutely obvious that China will have a large swath of the area of supply chain management for the global pharmaceutical industry, mainly attributing to its stronghold of raw materials and bulk drugs, the complete impact of COVID-19 on the pharmaceutical supply chains may not be uncovered for months.

A majority of Contract Development and Manufacturing Organizations (CDMOs) and many other Western pharmaceutical companies have been washing their hands to cut costs and wash their hands of chemicals and pharmaceutical raw ingredients that are fatal for the environment by moving their manufacturing plants to China and India. However, now this has created major challenges for these companies to evaluate and enhance the global footprint of their supply chains in order to keep their businesses from dying.

4.2 Back-up Locations and Alternate Distribution Routes & Channels

The novel coronavirus has not only spread through human bodies but it has also had a major impact on various elements of pharmaceutical supply chains. Primary areas of pharmaceutical businesses that will witness this impact are locations of manufacturing plants, testing facilities, workforce, as well as the distribution routes and sales channels.

Leading players in the pharmaceutical industry are moving on to creating a new business continuity plan to keep going on with their supply chain operations amidst the global lockdown. Use of alternative locations for all the important supply chain operations including clinical trials and virtual interactions between healthcare professionals and participants.

In addition, the regulatory framework for the pharmaceutical industry is also expected to undergo a tectonic shift, which will impact the import-export and distribution barriers for pharmaceutical businesses. Most governments are likely to appreciate domestic control of pharmaceutical supply chains in the coming years, while leading market players are likely to leverage advanced technologies to explore digital and virtual ways to review their risk management plans.

However, pharmaceutical businesses are still likely to struggle with the implementation of such drastic changes in supply chain operations and its elements such as distribution channels, packaging standards, virtual trial design, and expiry or temperature profiling. Though there is an immense potential for capitalizing on next-generation technologies, unavailability of raw materials and foreign-sourced production will continue to have a substantial impact on both production and supply chain management of pharmaceutical businesses.

5. COVID-19 and its Impact on Marketing Models of Pharmaceutical Businesses

While there are a large number of factors such as consumers, healthcare organizations, academic bodies, and other healthcare personnels, that influence marketing models for

pharmaceutical companies, COVID-19 has emerged as a game changer. Its worldwide outbreak has had a significant impact on end-users' purchasing behaviour, while most of the changing regulatory aspects are creating challenges for pharmaceutical businesses for gaining marketing authorisations.

5.1 Marketing Strategy of In-person Engagement Remains Off-limits

In developed regions, such as North America and European Union, the marketing strategies for pharmaceutical businesses are heavily regulated by policymakers. Furthermore, provision and funding mechanisms are also managed by risk pooling through insurance schemes. However, various dynamics are changed since the novel coronavirus pandemic.

All healthcare and life science organizations are facing severe challenges not only in keeping up with production and distribution, but ensuring end-user engagement has become among the prominent ones. In-person engagement has always proven to be one of the most effective marketing strategies for pharmaceutical businesses for many years. However, the outbreak of COVID-19 has changed that equation.

The representatives of pharmaceutical companies are unable to visit healthcare professionals anymore, which is restricting them from practising the age-old and proven marketing tradition. Constantly changing drivers and challenges for the new pharmaceutical market during and post the COVID-19 pandemic will call for a continuous effort for pharmaceutical businesses to identify new ways of engaging their customers.

5.2 New Ways of Marketing and Advertising are the Silver Lining for Pharmaceutical Businesses

Marketing is among the only business units that can discover new opportunities of boosting operations in the middle of the global lockdown. Digital marketing is booming in the current times, helping businesses bolster the sales potential of their products, and a large number of pharmaceutical companies are likely to jump the bandwagon. They are increasing their focus on changing the way they can interact with their target customers - which is widely going digital across most regions of the world.

The new barriers that their customers are facing can be easily resolved through digital media, and this is exactly what will influence the digital marketing strategies for pharmaceutical business in the coming years. For instance, Direct-to-Consumer Advertising (DTCA) is expected to be implemented digitally by businesses to influence consumers' purchasing behaviour through their attitude, perception, and knowledge.

Digital marketing for pharmaceutical businesses can meet three of their major requirements - strategic coordination and information sharing; development of differentiating competencies

of their products; and enhancing end-user experience through e-commerce. These strategies can ultimately act as a boon for other business operations for pharmaceutical companies during the rise of COVID-19 pandemic.

6. Inference

6.1 Conclusion

The tantalizing glimpses into the epidemiology of the current COVID-19 pandemic has created new barriers for the pharmaceutical industry. However, it has also given rise to new opportunities for businesses that manage to remain resilient during this hard time.

Governing bodies are likely to develop new frameworks of regulations that will emphasize the importance of local businesses. While focusing on major supply chain issues such as shortage of APIs or bulk drugs and other key raw materials, a majority of governing bodies worldwide are making decisions to devise a long-term investment plan to support clean and environmentally friendly production activities of local pharmaceutical businesses.

Pharmaceutical businesses will have to shift their focus on domestic production, reducing their dependence on raw materials that come in from the overseas, alternative distribution channels, and digital ways of marketing their products. The advent of new technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning will also have a great impact on the way pharmaceutical businesses have been operating since the past few years.

Though the current scenario does not seem very optimistic for businesses all around the globe, as big economies like Japan are slipping into recession, leading pharmaceutical businesses are preparing themselves to deal with the situation by leveraging the tool of technology. Pharmaceutical industry has always been a data-rich industry, which opens doors for data science and data engineering tools that can utilize 'information' to extract 'insights'.

Adopting a more disciplined approach towards adopting the strategies of integrating next-generation technologies that suit the digital age will soon become the new normal for pharmaceutical businesses. Right application of technologies and leveraging new government investment plans to boost production are among the most important ways that can solve this Gordian knot and help businesses in successfully dealing with and surviving the pandemic.

6.2 Limitations

- This research paper does not take into consideration the potential changes in geopolitical conditions and their impact on pharmaceutical businesses.

- This research paper does not focus on the impact of COVID-19 on pharmaceutical businesses across a particular geographical region.

7. References

1. Sushmita A. Narayana, Rupesh Kumar Pati, Prem Vrat, (2012),"Research on management issues in the pharmaceutical industry: a literature review", International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing, Vol. 6 Iss: 4 pp. 351 - 375
2. Jha, Raghendra and Sharma, Ashok, India's Pharmaceutical Industry: Global Supply Chain and Governance in the Post- COVID-19 World (June 9, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3622794> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3622794>
3. Sanders JM, Monogue ML, Jodlowski TZ, Cutrell JB. Pharmacologic Treatments for Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A Review. JAMA. 2020;323(18):1824–1836. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.6019
4. NSD Bio Group, LLC. (2010) Potential Health & Safety Impacts from Pharmaceuticals and Supplements Containing Chinese-Sourced Raw Ingredients, pp 04-16.
5. Pratap Khedkar and Saby Mitra. (2017) Boosting Pharmaceutical Sales and Marketing with Artificial Intelligence, pp 03-07.
6. James K. Jackson, Martin A. Weiss, Andres B. Schwarzenberg, Rebecca M. Nelson. (2020) Global Economic Effects of COVID-19, R46270, pp 12-24.
7. Uday Raj Sharma. NiraliPrakashan. (2012) Pharmaceutical Marketing Management.
8. McKinsey Report. (2020) COVID-19: Implications for business.
9. Matt Craven, Mihir Mysore, and Matthew Wilson, (May 2020) McKinsey and Company: COVID-19 briefing note, pp 03-04.
10. Chemical & Engineering News (C&EN), American Chemical Society
11. American Marketing Association
12. The International Society for Pharmaceutical Engineering